
The Relationship of Response Time and Therapeutic Communication Capability of Nurses on Patient Satisfaction

Imam Subeki¹, Imelda Aqhna Ariyani²

^{1,2}Program Studi Sarjana Terapan Keperawatan Poltekkers Kemenkes Malang

INTRODUCTION

Dissatisfaction with health services is a situation where consumer expectations are not the same or higher than the performance received from the service (Kotler and Keller, 2018). Factors that can cause patient dissatisfaction in the Emergency Room (IGD) are the staff's less communicative attitude and slow response time where patients are not treated quickly. Nurses' communication skills and fast response time are important in-patient satisfaction (Karin, 2018). The satisfaction felt by patients is closely related to the services provided by nurses in the ER (Dewi, 2019). If needs are not met, consumers may switch to other services (Linda, 2018). Based on data from the World Health Organization (WHO) Southeast Asia Region in 2019, it shows that around 45% of health service users were satisfied with the services provided, around 55% stated they were dissatisfied with the services provided (Septiadi, 2019). Dissatisfaction with health services in Indonesia in 2019 reached 28.76% (RI Ministry of Health, 2019). In East Java Province, emergency room patient dissatisfaction in 2019 reached 34.70% (East Java Health Office, 2019). According to the 2019 Republic of Indonesia Ministry of Health Regulations, the Minimum Service Standard for patient satisfaction is above 95%. If health services are found with a satisfaction level below 95%, it is considered that the services provided do not meet minimum standards, and the level of patient satisfaction is low (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2019).

The results of Virgo's research (2018) in the emergency room at Bangkinang Regional Hospital regarding the relationship between response time for emergency room services for 98 respondents, the results showed that there was a relationship between response time and the level of patient satisfaction. Likewise, the results of Karame & Husain's (2019) research on the Relationship between Nurse Response Time and Patient Satisfaction in the Emergency Room at Sanana Hospital on 38 respondents, the results show that there is a relationship between Nurse response time and Patient Satisfaction. This shows that response time in the ER has an impact on patient satisfaction with the services provided. Kusumo's research (2017) in the emergency room at Yogyakarta Regional Hospital found that nurses' therapeutic communication had an effect on patient satisfaction in the emergency room. Research by Meikayanti et al (2020) regarding the relationship between nurses' therapeutic communication and patient satisfaction at the Tabanan Regency Regional Hospital with a total of 67 respondents, with the results that there was a relationship between nurses' therapeutic communication and patient satisfaction. Muninjaya (2004) states that communication is a factor that influences patient satisfaction. Therapeutic communication is the process of providing advice to patients to support planned healing efforts, where information is given well and patient complaints are handled quickly by nurses. However, no research has yet been conducted that combines response time and therapeutic communication of nurses in the Emergency Room with patient satisfaction. Based on this, researchers are interested in conducting research on the relationship between response time and nurses' therapeutic communication skills on patient satisfaction, especially in the emergency room installation at Lavalette Hospital of Malang City.

METHODS

This research method uses a cross-sectional design. The research sample was patients who were being treated in the emergency room Lavalette Hospital of Malang City with a total of 92 respondents. The sampling method uses accidental sampling. The data collection method uses observation of the time it takes for nurses to carry out initial actions and questionnaires on nurse therapeutic communication and patient satisfaction. Bivariate analysis used Spearman-rho analysis and multivariate analysis used multiple linear regression with $\alpha = <0.05$.

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RESULT

1. Nurse Response Time

Table 1. Response Time for Nurses in the Emergency Room at Lavalette Hospital, Malang, March – April 2024

Priority	Category		f (n=92)		(%)	
	Fast	Slow	Fast	Slow		
P1	48	11	59	50,0	13,1	63,1
P2	9	3	12	10,0	4,1	14,1
P3	17	4	21	18,8	4,0	22,8
Totally	74	18	92	78,8	21,2	100

Based on Table 1, it shows that the response time of nurses in P1 in the fast category was 50.0%, in P3 in the fast category it was 18.8%, in P2 in the fast category it was 10.0%. The response time of nurses in the fast category is 78.8% and the response time of nurses in the slow category is 21.2%

2. Therapeutic Communication Skills

Table 2 Therapeutic Communication Skills of Nurses in the Emergency Room at Lavalette Hospital, Malang, March – April 2024

Therapeutic Communication Skills	f (n=92)	(%)
Good	76	82,6
Enough	2	2,2
Not Enough	14	15,2
Total	92	100

Based on Table 2 The therapeutic communication skills of nurses in the Emergency Room at Lavalette Hospital Malang are in the good category, namely 82.6%, in the poor category it is 15.2%, in the sufficient category it is 2.2%.

3. Patient Satisfaction

Table 3 Patient Satisfaction in the Emergency Room at Lavalette Hospital, Malang, March – April 2024

Satisfaction	f (n=92)	(%)
Very satisfied	28	30,5
Satisfied	44	47,8
Not Satisfied	20	21,7
Very Not Satisfied	0	0
Totally	92	100

Based on Table 3, patient satisfaction at the Lavalette Hospital Malang Emergency Room is classified as 47.8% satisfied, 30.5% in the very satisfied category, 21.7% in the dissatisfied category and there are no patients who feel very dissatisfied. satisfied with the service at the Lavalette Hospital Malang Emergency Room

4. Relationship between response time and patient satisfaction

Table 4. Relationship between response time and patient satisfaction in the emergency department at Lavalette Hospital, Malang, March – April 2024

Respon Time	Patient Satisfaction				Total	P-value R
	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfaction	Very Satisfaction		
Fast	0	20	32	22	74	0,000 0,788
Slow	0	0	12	6	18	
Total	0	20	44	28	92	

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Based on Table 4 of the Relationship between Response Time and Patient Satisfaction in the Emergency Room at Lavalette Hospital, Malang, the p-value = 0.000 ($\alpha < 0.05$) and the r-square value = 0.788. H_a is accepted, which means the relationship between response time and patient satisfaction is significant and strong

5. Relationship between Nurses' Therapeutic Communication Skills and Patient Satisfaction

Table 5: The Relationship between Nurses' Therapeutic Communication Skills and Patient Satisfaction in the Emergency Room at Lavalette Hospital, Malang, March - April 2024

Therapeutic Communication Skills	Patient Satisfaction				Total	P Value	R
	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Satisfaction	Very Satisfaction			
Notb Enough	0	14	0	0	14	0,000	0,641
Enaough	0	1	1	0	2		
Good	0	5	43	28	76		
Total	0	20	44	28	92		

Based on Table 5, the relationship between therapeutic communication skills and patient satisfaction in the Emergency Department at Lavalette Hospital, Malang, shows a p-value = 0.000 ($\alpha < 0.05$) and an r-square value = 0.641. H_a is accepted, which means that the relationship between nurses' therapeutic communication skills and patient satisfaction is significant and strong.

6. The Relationship between Response Time and Nurses' Therapeutic Communication Skills on Patient Satisfaction

Table 6: The Relationship between Response Time and Nurses' Therapeutic Communication Skills on Patient Satisfaction in the Emergency Room at Lavalette Hospital, Malang, March - April 2024

Regression Logistik Test	P-Value	R-Square	Level of Significifant
	0.000	0.745	Significant and Strong Relationship

Based on Table 6, the relationship between response time and nurses' therapeutic communication skills on patient satisfaction in the Lavalette Hospital Emergency Room, the p-value = 0.000 ($\alpha < 0.05$) and the r-square value = 0.745. H_a is accepted, which means that the relationship between response time and nurses' therapeutic communication skills on patient satisfaction is strong and significant

CONCLUSION

The results of statistical tests using speraman-rho obtained a p-value of 0.000 ($\alpha < 0.005$). H_a is accepted, so it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between nurse response time and patient satisfaction. The correlation coefficient (r) is 0.788, which means the level of closeness is strong. This finding is in line with research by Basri et al (2023) in the emergency room at Sekarwangi Sukabumi Hospital with 97 respondents. The result was p-value = 0.000, which means there is a significant relationship between nurse response time and patient satisfaction levels. Another study by Sugiono and Muflihatin (2022) in the emergency room of Abdul Wahab Sjahrani Hospital, Samarinda with 97 respondents, the statistical test results showed p value = 0.002, so there is a significant relationship between response time and patient satisfaction level. Furthermore, research by Simandalahi et al (2019) In the emergency room at the Tiban Baru Community Health Center with 74 respondents, the statistical test results showed p = 0.039, which means there is a relationship between response time and patient satisfaction. The results of this study show that there is a significant relationship between nurse response time and patient satisfaction. This indicates the importance of fast and efficient response time from medical personnel, especially nurses, in handling patients in order to increase patient satisfaction. A good response time for patients is <5 minutes (Pira er al., 2021). The impact of fast response time is very significant on patient satisfaction. Fast response time not only increases patient satisfaction but can prevent the risk of disability and even patient death. Fast response time can provide a sense of security and attention to patients, which in turn can increase consumer perceptions of service quality. On the other hand, a slow response time can cause patient dissatisfaction and can cause harm to the patient. To improve response time in the ER, several efforts can be made, such as increasing the number of medical personnel to reduce workload and increase service efficiency, ongoing training to increase skills and speed in handling emergency cases. Improved coordination and communication between teams to ensure fast and appropriate handling. Patients who are treated quickly and effectively tend to feel more satisfied with the services provided. This means increasing response time as a strategy that can improve service quality The results of statistical tests using Spearman Rho obtained a p-value of 0.000 ($\alpha < 0.005$). H_a was accepted, so it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between nurses' therapeutic communication skills and patient satisfaction. The correlation

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coefficient (r) is 0.641, which means the level of closeness is strong. The results of this research are in line with research by Meikayanti et al (2020) at the Tabanan District Hospital with 67 respondents and obtained a p-value of 0.00, so it was concluded that there was a significant relationship between nurses' therapeutic communication and patient satisfaction. Another study by Basri et al (2023) in the emergency room of a hospital Sekarwangi Sukabumi West Java with 97 respondents, obtained a p-value of 0.000, which means there is a relationship between therapeutic communication skills and the level of patient satisfaction. Likewise, research by Hayati et al (2023) in the Emergency Room of RS Sekarwangi Sukabumi regarding the relationship between nurses' therapeutic communication and patient family satisfaction in the Emergency Room of RSUD Dr. Soediran Mangun Sumarso with 92 respondents, obtained p value = 0.00, it was concluded that there was a relationship between nurses' therapeutic communication and patient satisfaction. These studies show that effective communication has a significant impact on patient satisfaction. Agil et al (2022) emphasize the importance of the nurse-patient relationship built through therapeutic interactions to achieve treatment goals effectively. Patients who feel that nurses' activities are in line with their expectations will have a positive impact on patient satisfaction, which in turn will influence the quality of hospital services. Quality therapeutic communication skills can help build trusting relationships, improving the image of the hospital and the nursing profession. Thus, it is important for nurses to build a relationship of mutual trust with patients through effective therapeutic communication. The results of the logistic regression test showed a p-value of 0.000, meaning that the alpha was smaller than the significance level of 0.05. This shows that the response time and communication skills of nurses have a significant influence on patient satisfaction at the Lavalette Hospital, Malang. The r-square value of 0.745 shows that the logistic regression model used has good predictive power in explaining the relationship between these variables. This means that the faster the nurse's response time and the better the nurse's therapeutic communication skills, the higher the level of patient care. This means that both variables have a significant contribution in predicting patient satisfaction. This is in line with Nurudin's (2020) research regarding the relationship between response time and nurses' therapeutic communication skills on patient satisfaction in the emergency room at Sekarwangi Hospital, Sukabumi. These findings provide practical implications for hospital management to take strategic steps to improve these two factors, such as providing training to nurses to improve therapeutic communication skills and optimizing work flow to speed up nurse response time in handling patients in the ER. It is hoped that these efforts can improve service quality and patient satisfaction

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